

Class Collabs: Assessing Inter-disciplinary Relationship Building in Media Education

Paul Ziek
Pace University, USA
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9328-0387>

Abstract

Contrary to popular belief, higher education does not exist in an ivory tower. Indeed, higher education is no stranger to adopting and implementing new pedagogical approaches and trends. One endeavor is the class collaboration, or Class Collab, which is a form of instruction that integrates the learning community with experiential learning. Although the basis for the class collaboration dates to Dewey, no studies have assessed this education model as it exists within media education. Given this gap in the literature, the current study uses a small sample pretest-posttest design to explore the impact of class collaborations with film and public relations courses. The results show that there are differences between the pretest and posttest data and that overall, the Class Collab is associated with positive learning outcomes. However, an emergent finding within the data is that there was an overwhelming number of students that described difficulty working across industries, especially as it relates to communication. The result is that students working to create interdisciplinary media products need more of an understanding in the strategic elements of communication.

Keywords: collaboration, experiential learning, learning communities, assessment

Introduction

In an attempt to change the static nature of course content, over the years, higher education has worked to embrace new technologies such as radio, television, one-to-one-computing (Cuban, 2001) as well as practices such as distance education, the flipped classroom and freshman interest groups (Altbach, Reisberg & Rumbley, 2019). One of the more inventive endeavors in this line of thinking is the

class collaboration, or Class Collab, which is a form of instruction that integrates the learning community with experiential learning. Class Collabs are voluntary relationships among multiple classes that amplify or replicate real world instances by immersing students in guided learning situations. Class Collabs follow Peppers's (2016) contention that higher education needs to become collaborative in a way that it helps students meet the challenges of a knowledge-based economy. Although there have been anecdotal descriptions of successful Class Collabs (Ziek & Fink, 2019; Guarneri, Ziek & Freeman, 2020), more research is needed on the impact they have on student learning.

According to Haywood (2000), assessment is typically viewed in terms of accreditation, but it is actually a multidimensional process that helps educators judge programs and initiatives. Although assessment has been an aspect of higher education for decades, it has taken on new meaning recently. Indeed, Calhoun and Green (2015) argue that since institutions are expected to make economic, social and cultural contributions, it is crucial to be able to make conceptual and practical generalizations about the validity and reliability of newly adopted trends. Since Class Collabs are based on knowledge building outcomes, it is necessary to draw scientific conclusions about their impact on student learning. Therefore, the current study will assess a Class Collab to draw research and practice closer in a way that professionally based education can be better matched to the conditions of the actual environment.

Learning Communities Assessment

Since their conception over 80 years ago by Dewey (1938), learning communities have become a conventional aspect of academia. Yet, there is still debate in the literature on the most appropriate definition (see Beck, 1999). No matter the approach, most definitions have the same underlying principle. Overall, as Lenning and Ebbers (2013) explain, a learning community is "an intentionally developed community that exists to promote and maximize the individual and shared learning of its members" (p. 7). There are four basic models of learning community: linked courses, course clusters, freshman interest groups and coordinated studies. All of these methods attain what Mitchell and Stackney (2011) describe as the pivotal dimensions of a learning community: they impact participants' personal (active and reflective creation of knowledge), interpersonal (construction of collective meaning) and organizational (building of systems that support all ideas) capacity. In this way, learning communities work to promote intellectual interaction through a coherent collaborative structure.

Of course, as with everything, there are criticisms. Timbur (1989) argues that the use of consensus in learning creates a type of group think and stifles individual voice and creativity. Forman and Ansell (2001) found an opposite effect where the public dialogue and deep understanding incubated in learning communities promotes tension and con-

flict among all the participants, both instructor and student. DuFour (2004) contends that learning communities have become so ubiquitous that the term in general and goals and objectives more specifically are in danger of losing all meaning. Along these lines, Brown, Hansen-Brown and Conte (2011) maintain that one of the reasons for this is that learning communities focus mostly on theoretical knowledge as opposed to hands-on student learning and assessment. The point here is that although learning communities are a great departure from the dominant approaches of higher education there is still more to be done to build what Bielaczyc and Collins (1999) describe as a culture where all the participants are involved in the collective effort of understanding.

Experiential Learning

Dewey (1938) didn't only map out the learning community but also experiential learning – he encouraged the cultivation of student experiences as a way to construct knowledge. Experiential learning emphasizes a holistic approach to education by stressing practice and consequently understanding of the practice, as opposed to just consideration of theoretical paradigms (Kohonen, 2007). Although it has been around in some form or fashion for decades, experience-based education became popular in the 1970s as a reaction to the widespread criticism of what the public perceived as static teaching methodologies. However, it wasn't until Kolb and Kolb (1985) developed Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) that the process began to find a permanent home in many colleges and universities. According to Kolb and Kolb, ELT is a framework where different types of learning can occur - all of which rely on how individuals encounter and contemplate occurrences. Within ELT, there are two main components: the experience and the reflective activity related to the experience (Boud, Keogh, & Walker, 1985). As far as research on experiential learning is concerned, the experience portion has been discussed considerably more often than that of reflection.

Experiential learning, in much the same way as learning communities, has become a highly used model of education as institutions all over the world have adopted some form of hands-on learning (Austin & Rust, 2015). Experiential learning is particularly important in the areas where students work on both the theoretical and practical skills needed to be media makers and content creators. Media and communication scholars often turn to experiential learning to engage students in the practices involved with performing, evaluating, and reflecting on the work done in the media creation. Typically, experiential learning occurs through internships, case studies and service learning. Although these forms of experiential learning do well to get students engaged with the material, they still miss many of the practices involved in creating media content (Ziek & Fink, 2018). What cuts across both areas, learning communities and experiential learning, is that neither prepare students with the necessary workplace skills that optimize their talents such as “soft skills.” Soft skills

include socio-emotional abilities such as communication, negotiation, and social participation as well as conflict resolution, negotiation or the relationship management that is specific to creating media content. In other words, when learning communities and experiential learning are used in the areas of media and communication, there is little involvement with, and understanding of how to attract and retain clients, negotiate contracts, coordinate interdisciplinary labor and network across organizations. Instead, students focus on specific industry tasks such as writing press releases, scripts or articles, filming, recording, editing, etc. To overcome these missing elements, many media and communication instructors have developed the notion of the Class Collab. The Class Collab is a form of education that melds multiple classes so that coursework is pointed toward applied competencies and understandings relative to a field or industry (Ziek, 2021).

Class Collabs

Collaboration is a strategic behavior where technological, human and social capital are shared for the purposes of value creation. In higher education, what often comes to mind are collaborations that bring together universities with school systems and government entities for practice-based nursing or social service education or when universities partner with each other to offer universal access such as with edX. Collaboration in this sense is meant to help solve some of the systemic social and environmental issues that underlie the health and safety of the entire population. Recently however, collaborations have moved to a more micro level with the adoption of Class Collabs. Class Collabs are centered on purposeful course alignment so that activities encompass both assignments and projects as well as student cooperation. Class Collabs simply do not consist of multiple courses synchronizing learning theories or objectives but developing an opportunity for genuine engagement with the material and other students. More specifically, the Class Collab relies on the specific form of learning communities that features cooperative learning techniques (e.g., Lenning & Ebbers, 1999) where the locus of the community is to engage in hands-on activities. The emphasis of the Class Collab is to combine courses in a way that there is an inherent value in the investment made by the individual students. Even though instructors have adopted this model without the moniker, to this point there has been no research on the legitimacy of the Class Collab. Therefore, the current study asks: What is the impact of class collabs on student learning?

To answer this research question requires undertaking an assessment project. Assessment, as Boud and Falchikov (2007) explain, is a value laden activity that measures the quality and standards of academic activities. Since assessment is a principal guarantor of quality assurance as Bryan and Clegg (2019) argue, the benefits of the current study are to verify the reliability of a codified Class Collab. The Class

Collab at the center of this study occurred at a mid-sized university based in the Northeastern United States and brought together students from the areas of public relations and filmmaking. The overall goal of the Class Collab was to have students perform the specific activities related to their field as well as work on areas that are not typically part of either learning communities or experiential learning such as building inter-disciplinary or inter-organizational relationships, creating Work Breakdown Structures with multiple parties, and developing and managing budgets and change orders, to name a few.

Method

Determining the impact of a Class required assessment of student progress over time (Haywood, 2000). The primary method of collecting data was a pretest-post design, which allowed the measurement of variables on different occasions. Pretest-post designs are widely used because they allow for the comparison of paired data without disrupting the research setting and consequently improve external validity (Dimitrov & Rumrill, 2003). This is particularly important because the current study focused only on one Class Collab. In other words, a single small nonrandomized group of students were evaluated before the collab began and after the collab ended to determine if there were any differences (Bonate, 2000). The pretest involved determining what the students knew about their primary area and how much inter-disciplinary work they have done in the past. The posttest determined how much knowledge they acquired in each area. Both pretest and posttest were accomplished through surveys that included Likert and open-ended questions.

The Class Collab at the center of the current study occurred between January 2021 and May 2021 and involved three courses: Media Production I; The Film Remake; and Writing Public Relations Copy. A total of 60 students participated: 38 students on the film production side (Media Production I, The Film Remake) and 22 dedicated to promotion (Writing Public Relations Copy). There were two learning objectives relative to the Class Collab, no matter what course: students had to work across disciplines; and students had to hone the skills relative to their functional areas. The deliverable output of the collab was a full scene remake from a blockbuster. Therefore, the classes had to engage in pre-production (i.e. script, storyboards and shot lists, getting the crew, location scouting, budgeting, etc.), production (i.e. principal photography) and postproduction (i.e. editing, sound mixing, special effects, etc.). To do this, students were placed in 5 groups and then paired across courses. In other words, each “remake team” consisted of a group of students from Media Production I, The Film Remake and Writing Public Relations Copy. Groups were given specific assignments to assure they practiced the tasks associated with the course as well as work across disciplines. For example, the Film Remake groups acted as producer and director and engaged in much of the overall planning. This included being responsible for the preproduction phase and pitch-

ing the specific remake to the faculty, developing the script, storyboards, shot lists, convening a crew, scouting locations, casting and crafting a budget. The Media Production I groups were responsible for principal photography, that is, they acted as the primary film crew, and they handled the bulk of the editing. Both the Media Production and Film Remake groups worked with the public relations students to create a promotional plan which was complete with goals and objectives, stakeholders and key messages, strategies and tactics and timeline and budget.

Results

Pretest Data

The pretest data showed that the filmmakers held a moderate amount of experience (mean = 3.25, SD = 1.13) and confidence (mean = 3.05, SD = .086) in their abilities. Essentially, they had no strong positive or negative belief in their filmmaking skills. When asked about their experience with interdisciplinary work (mean = 1.12, SD = 0.091), they had a skewed view of their proficiency. In other words, the filmmakers involved in the collaboration were aware they lacked experience and knowledge working across fields. In much the same way, the public relations practitioners held a similar view of their personal experience (mean = 3.70, SD = 0.91) and confidence (mean = 3, SD = 0.88) in the process of building good will through communication. In addition, when asked about their know-how and familiarity with filmmaking, the public relations practitioners (mean = 4.11, SD = 0.65) overwhelmingly answered they did not have much. Again, in much the same way as the filmmakers, 78% involved in public relations admitted to having been involved in very little interdisciplinary work.

The posttest information showed several points of improvement after the collaboration. For the filmmakers, 70% answered that their skills improved and 90% stated that the collaboration positively impacted their confidence (mean = 2.01, SD = 0.07). Likewise, the filmmakers felt their knowledge about public relations also increased (mean = 2.9, SD = 1.07) with 65% explaining that they knew more about public relations after the collaboration than at any other time. Table 1 details some of the more apposite quotes relating to the lessons learned of filmmakers after the collaboration.

The public relations posttest told a similar story to that of the filmmakers. 95% of the public relations practitioners felt strongly that their skills (mean = 2.21, SD = 1.06). The students also learned about filmmaking beyond what they had already known (mean = 3.37, SD = 1.04). Following along these lines, their knowledge about what it takes to work with groups outside of public relations increased (mean = 2.47, SD = 1.31) dramatically with 79% agreeing that it enhanced their confidence with other fields (mean = 2.27, SD = 1.12). Table 2 includes a sample of quotes from the public relations students.

Table 1
Filmmakers Lessons Learned
Being in charge of thinking through everything that goes into making a movie helps in understanding what it is really like to work in the film industry.
I learned more about the business side of filmmaking and that PR is a large part of it.
I got to learn more about how a film should be promoted instead of what we usually do as filmmakers.
I was able to learn a lot more of what PR people do, especially as they managed the social media.
I learned that PR helps a lot during post-production, and it is why I enjoyed doing it so much with the group.

Beyond increased competency and confidence, there was an emergent theme in the results. 13% of the students described difficulties with communication, and the need to actively seek interventions to overcome these difficulties. As noted earlier, the Class Collab took place during the Covid-19 pandemic, therefore there was a heavy reliance on technology. Although in-person communication and interaction did take place, the majority occurred via e-mail, text, Zoom or Discord. While Generation Z, a.k.a. “zoomers”, are accustomed to using information and communication technologies (ICTs), they encounter the same issues that

Table 2
Public Relations Practitioners Lessons Learned
This was very interesting for me as I was able to apply the terms and methods we discussed in class in a real-world setting.
I knew little to nothing before enrolling in this class about film and learned how to promote an actual production.
From writing the script, figuring out location, lighting, sound, etc. there were many aspects that I had not even considered when we started putting together the promotional plan.
I did get to see just how much work goes into the behind the scenes into the making of the film.
I learned new skills that were different from last semester especially with something that is not my major.

have plagued virtual teams for years (see McGraw & Stewart, 2020. In particular there were a set of microlevel problems that subsequently impacted higher macrolevel interactions (Ziek & Smulowitz, 2014).

On a micro level, the students detailed failed attempts at simply connecting with each other, which subsequently impacted their ability to coordinate activity. Delays in responses, lack of commitment, and inefficient use of time denied some of the groups, and students,

an opportunity for sustain dialogue on the project. In other words, by not exchanging information efficiently, some groups, and students, ended up working in silos or had to wait until they were physically together to complete some important tasks. Table 3 includes comments related to the microlevel difficulties and failures.

Table 3
Microlevel Communication Issues
Since the other group did not answer emails for days, it was difficult to get on the same page.
We met with the production group once a week but the meetings weren't structured, so we just ended up talking about our favorite movies most of the time.
Not everyone could meet at the same time and so everyone was on a different schedule and we had to work twice as hard on the production schedule.
No one was held accountable when they didn't show up to film the scene. The worst part is that when people missed filming, we had to make up for the missing crew member.
There was a severe lack of communication on all levels and we needed an outside force to get people to actually work on something.

The macrolevel problems of communication were amplified by the microlevel. In other words, since the groups had a difficult time organizing, there were issues with the creative aspects of the project. When the groups were stalled by, and mired in, the low-level aspects of communication such as coordinating interactions, such as answering emails or deciding when or how to meet, problems were carried over to the larger craft of generating content. In other words, when communication failed, the groups had difficulty with planning and executing everything from script and storyboard creation, to shot lists, the work breakdown of principal photography to editing, and promoting the remake to make sure there were interested viewers. Table 4 includes comments related to the macrolevel difficulties and failures.

The results of this single subject pre-test post-test showed that there are differences between the first and second measurement in an increase of knowledge about specific technical areas as well as working across disciplinary lines. On one hand, the pre-test of the The results of this single subject pre-test post-test showed that there are differences between the first and second measurement in an increase of knowledge about specific technical areas as well as working across disciplinary lines. On one hand, the pre-test of the filmmakers gauged what they knew about production techniques, public relations and interdisciplinary groups prior to the collaboration, and the posttest showed how this knowledge increased after the collaboration. On the other hand, the pre-test of the public relations students measured what they knew about communication campaigns, filmmaking and interdisciplinary relationships prior to the collaboration and the posttest showed how this knowledge also

Table 4
Macrolevel Communication Issues
It was difficult to agree on the visual syntax of the remake because until we sat down. All of the emails and discussions we had online were difficult and no one want to make a decision.
It was really hard to figure out the roles each of us would do on the shoot and then especially when it came to post-production.
It kind of felt like my group and I were just scraping by the entire semester, hoping that another the other group would help us with promoting our remake the way we envisioned it.
I feel that it was a struggle at first because everyone was on different pages with work and school schedules but eventually after a few meetings it turned out we decided on the same 'look' for the trailer.
This project really made me realize that when in a group, the more you talk the better your work will look when it comes to controlled media writing.

improved after the collaboration. In this sense, regarding the Research Question, the class collab had a positive impact on student learning and thus delivered a sound form of outcomes (e.g., Bloxham & Boyd, 2007). The overall assessment of the Class Collab illustrates that there were certainly achievements among the students. More specifically, the data showed that participants underwent developmental changes in that the Class Collab closed the gap between theoretical knowledge and practice or what Lipnevick, McCallen, Miles and Smith (2014) describe as the difference between real and normative performance.

Discussion

The current study unearthed an important element relative to course work that focuses on experiential, interdisciplinary learning in media and content creation. The lack of understanding about transactional communication can lead to breakdowns in group progress. Problems occur because students implicitly view communication in line with what Peters (1999) describes as a utopia of sharing between souls where nothing is misunderstood or misdirected. It is not until failure takes place that students revisit the notion, scope, and impact of communication. Indeed, Peters touches on this very subject by explaining that “miscommunication is the scandal that motivates the very concept of communication in the first place” (Peters, 1999, p. 6). The take-away is that courses based on experiential learning, particularly those that revolve around teaching interdisciplinary engagement, need to add components on functional and utilitarian communication.

Although media students understand that communication is the generative process behind media and content creation, they have little perspective on pragmatic communication – the communication that tends to be more theoretically designated as transmissive. This is not to say that the constitutive elements must be abandoned. In

fact, Rickard (2021) outlines that there are two functions of communication: pragmatic where senders direct messages at audiences with intended effects and a constitutive where these messages create context and meaning. Hence, there is a need to teach students how to produce operable letters, memos, meetings, conferences, e-mail, RFPs, RFQs. This can be achieved by integrating more material from the field of project management. Project management is the process where groups undertake temporary endeavors, which dovetails with the notion that media and content creation is an activity with a beginning and an end. Project management is also a professional practice of managerial knowledge that requires a multi-dimensional set of abilities and skills (Kerzner, 2019). The most important aspect of project management as it relates to the current study is that communication is viewed as “the provision of an appropriate network and necessary data to all key actors in the project implementation” (Slevin & Pinto, 1987, p. 34). Although the research on project management communication is extensive, for the purposes of the experiential, interdisciplinary learning, students should be trained using the Project Management Book of Knowledge (PMBOK) (PMI, 2021), which is the preeminent source for best practices in project management because it is continually updated to reflect the most effective standards. Equipped with a technical level of communicative understanding, students can build competencies in information delivery and transmission which will enable both the management of the context as well as the creation of a specific media product (Lauren & Schreiber, 2018).

Limitations

As with every study, the current one is not without limitations. The major limitation lies with the quantitative aspects. More specifically, the panel survey, which focused on the longitudinal measurement of the same groups over time, only includes 60 students. The result is that making any probability-based inferences to a wider population of filmmaking and public relations students is difficult. The limitation is balanced by the fact that the study is in line with Stake’s (1995) view of case studies where they focus on a particular and complex single case. The Class Collab at the center of the study is specific to one university and set of courses with a particular deliverable. Although the data shows that the Class Collab is an effective teaching strategy, generalizations must be made carefully. What is needed is more Class Collabs, and subsequently more assessment data, so that research can overcome Bryan and Clegg’s (2019) contention that most assessment often fails because it is a one-off that does not feed forward. Moreover, future Class Collabs should rely on different methods of data collection such as reflections, interviews and observation, all of which would avoid the shortcomings of small-scale quantitative data.

Conclusion

As noted by Chicioreanu and Amza (2018), there have been calls to adjust teaching styles to satisfy “zoomers” desire for experiential and interactive education. One of the more creative ways is the Class Collabs, which blends the learning community with experiential learning. Although Class Collaborations are nothing new, especially in media education, they still lack assessment. In other words, for decades media educators have been partnering to create innovative experiences for students yet to this point there has not been any attempt to determine the impact of these partnerships on learning. The current study assesses a Class Collab between three partnering courses where the delivery was a full scene remake from a blockbuster with related promotional activity. After a pretest – posttest survey of Likert and open-ended questions, the results show improvements in student knowledge and confidence after the collaboration. However, there was an unanticipated take-away from the study: the lack of practical experience in crafting emails, meetings, memos, and project plans hindered some of the more creative aspects of the collaboration, which can be corrected in the future by integrating components of project management education. Of course, when these soft skills are incorporated into Class Collabs, it will mean there is a need for even more assessment (Ricchiardi & Emanuel, 2018).

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